

Teacher's Perceived School-Level Psychosocial Environment and Self-Efficacy at Higher Education Institutions in Sulu

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Abstract: This study determined the extent of perceived self-efficacy and school-level psychosocial environment among college instructors at higher education institutions in Sulu during school year 2018-2019 and the significant relationship and differences in categories subsumed under these components when data are grouped according to age, gender, civil status, length of service, academic rank, highest educational qualification and type of higher education institution. This study answered the research questions based on the following hypotheses: (1) There is no significant relationship between teacher's perceived school-level psychosocial environment and self-efficacy at higher education institutions in Sulu; (2) There is no significant difference in teacher's perceived self-efficacy at higher education Institutions in Sulu when data are grouped according to: Age; Gender; Length of service; Academic rank; Educational Qualification; Employment status; and Type of HEI. (3) There is no significant difference in teacher's perceived school-level psychosocial environment at higher education Institutions in Sulu when data are grouped according to: Age; Gender; Length of service; Academic rank; Educational Qualification; Employment status; and Type of HEI. This study employed the descriptive-quantitative research design with 200 college instructors at higher education institutions in Sulu during the school year 2018-2019. The frequency counts and percentage score were used to determine the socio-demographic profiles; mean and standard deviation were used to determine the extent of teaching efficacy and school-level psychosocial environment. The *t*-Test for independent samples, One-Way ANOVA and Pearson Correlation Coefficient were used to determine the significant differences and degree of correlation of these variables. This following are findings of the study:

1. On students' demographic profile: 1.1. In terms of age, 40.5% of the instructors belong to age range of 31-40 years old; 1.2. In terms of gender, female college instructors constitute 55.0% while their male counterparts constitute 45.0% of the total 200 samples; 1.3. In terms of length of service, 47.0% have 10 years & below years of experience; 1.4. In terms of academic rank, 45.5% are Instructor (I, II, and III); constitutes, constitutes 51.20% are Teacher I. 1.5. In terms of highest educational attainment, 30.0% are having AB/BS + MA/MS Units; 1.6. In terms of employment status, 29.5% are contractual/job order and 44.0% with permanent status; and 1.7. In terms of type of HEI, 68.5% are public higher education institutions.
2. On extent of Teachers' self-efficacy: 2.1 On Efficacy for Student Engagement – instructors rated this category as Moderate Extent, 2.2 On Instructional strategies - instructors rated this category as Moderate Extent, 2.3 On Personal Teaching Efficacy - instructors rated this category as Moderate Extent.
3. On Extent of School-level Psychosocial environment: 3.1 On Relationship Dimension - instructors rated this category as High Extent, 3.2 On Personal Development Dimension – instructors rated this category as High Extent, 3.3 On System Maintenance/System Change Dimension - instructors rated this category as High Extent.

4. **On Correlation between Teachers' Self-Efficacy and School-Level Psychosocial environment:** 4.1 there is "Near Zero Correlation" between teachers' self-efficacy and school-level psychosocial environment.

5. **On differences in Teachers' Self-Efficacy:** 5.1 By Age, There is significant difference in teacher's perceived self-efficacy at higher education institutions in Sulu when data are grouped according to Age; Age 30 years & below are better perceivers of the extent of teaching efficacy in terms of student engagement; but age 21 years & above are better perceivers extent of teaching efficacy in terms of personal teaching efficacy, 5.2 By Gender, No significant difference in teacher's perceived self-efficacy at higher education institutions in Sulu when data are grouped according to gender, 5.3 By Length of Service, There is significant difference in teacher's perceived self-efficacy at higher education institutions in Sulu when data are grouped according to length of service. Instructors with 21 years & above of teaching experience are better perceivers the extent of teaching efficacy in terms of student engagement, 5.4 By Academic Rank, There is significant difference in teacher's perceived self-efficacy at higher education institutions in Sulu when data are grouped according to academic rank. Instructors with academic rank of a Prof. (I, II, III, IV, V, and VI) are better perceivers of the extent of teaching efficacy in terms of student engagement, 5.5 By Educational Attainment, No significant difference in teacher's perceived self-efficacy at higher education institutions in Sulu when data are grouped according to educational attainment. 5.6 By Employment Status, There is significant difference in teacher's perceived self-efficacy at higher education institutions in Sulu when data are grouped according to employment status. Instructors with permanent status of appointment are better perceivers of extent of teaching efficacy in terms of student engagement; instructional strategies and personal teaching efficacy, 5.7 By Type of HEI, There is significant difference in teacher's perceived self-efficacy at higher education institutions in Sulu when data are grouped according to type of higher educational institution.

6. **Difference in School-level Psychosocial Environment:** 6.1 By Age, There is significant difference in school-level psychosocial environment at higher education institutions in Sulu when data are grouped according to Age. With 30 years and below of age better perceivers of the extent of school-level psychosocial environment in terms of relationship dimension, personal development dimension and System Maintenance, 6.2 By Gender, There is significant difference in teacher's perceived school-level psychosocial environment at higher education institutions in Sulu when data are grouped according to gender. 6.3 By Length of service, there is significant difference in teacher's perceived school-level psychosocial environment at higher education institutions in Sulu when data are grouped according to length of service. With 10 years & below of length are better perceivers of the extent of school-level psychosocial environment in terms of relationship dimension, personal development dimension and System Maintenance, 6.4 By Academic Rank, No significant difference in teacher's perceived school-level psychosocial environment at higher education institutions in Sulu when data are grouped according to academic rank, 6.5 By Educational Qualification, No significant difference in teacher's perceived school-level psychosocial environment at higher education institutions in Sulu when data are grouped according to educational attainment, 6.6 By Employment Status, There is significant difference in teacher's perceived school-level psychosocial environment at higher education institutions in Sulu when data are grouped according to employment status. Contractual/Job Order status of appointment are better perceivers of the extent of school-level psychosocial environment in terms of relationship dimension and System Maintenance, 6.7 By Type of HEI, There is significant difference in teacher's perceived school-level psychosocial environment at higher education institutions in Sulu when data are grouped according to type of higher educational institution. It is concluded that respondents of this study are at age range of 31-40 years old; majority are female, have 10 years & below years of experience; Instructor (I, II, and III); having AB/BS + MA/MS Units; permanent status; and at public higher education institutions.

Teachers' self-efficacy is moderately rated, while school-level psychosocial environment rated as high extent with Near Zero Correlation between them. Yet, educational attainment, academic rank and gender have no influence on respondents' perceptions towards teachers' self-efficacy and school-level psychosocial environment. This particular study seems to support Bandura's (1989) Efficacy Theory when he stressed that the perceived self-efficacy or memory functioning is an important facet of meta-memory. Self-beliefs or efficacy can enhance or impair performance through their effects on cognitive, effective, or motivational intervening. Moreover, Bandura (1989) said that the psychosocial learning environment covers psychological and social factors that have consequences for satisfaction, health and ability to perform at learning places. The term psychosocial aspects of our experiences (e.g.

our thoughts, emotions and behaviors) and our wider social experience (e.g. our relationships, tradition and culture). Learners and teachers are psychologically affected by the surrounding social conditions that may disrupt or enhance the quality and effectiveness of learning. The question is how to endure every learner an environment that is physically safe, emotionally secure and psychologically enabling. It is recommended that higher education institutions in the province Sulu may venture into reviewing the programs and activities to include those that cater to the improvement of social learning environment of college students; prompt and adequacy of overload pay; Processes and programs to reduce job insecurity. The educational attainment and academic rank showed significant effect to school-level psychosocial environment, thus it is mostly recommended that the faculty should pursue advance education in their field specialization. Issues and concerns relating to provision of conducive social learning should be given a serious attention. That is, public higher education institutions should devise programs and strategies that shall promote better learning conditions via individual and work interventions.

Keywords: Educational Qualification, Employment status, demographic profile, Length of service, Psychosocial environment, Self-efficacy.

I. INTRODUCTION

The transition of students from senior high school to tertiary level of learning institution carries a major life change that may affect Teachers' teaching behavior. That is, on students' part, entering the institution of higher learning may be a source of strain and an acute stressor (Friedlander et al., 2007). At the colleges and universities, academic demands increase and new social relations are established. Difficulties in handling the stressors/challenges associated with the transition may lead to decreased academic performance and increased psychological distress (Friedlander et al., 2007).

The important components to perceive school-level psychosocial environment and self-efficacy at higher education institutions in Sulu, is the people's beliefs about their capabilities to produce designated levels of performance that exercise influence over events that affect their lives. Adjustment is a continual process by which a person varies his/her behavior to produce a more harmonious relationship between himself/herself and his/her environment (Aggarwal, 1998). It implies changes in our thinking and way of life to the demands of the situation. Based on the above definitions, adjustment could be seen as a condition or state in which one feels that one's needs have been (or will be) fulfilled and one's behaviors conforms to the needs of a given environment. It determines how people feel, think, motivate themselves and behave. Such beliefs produce these diverse effects through four major processes. They include cognitive, motivational, affective and selection processes.

Psychosocial approach looks at the combined influenced that psychological factors and the surrounding social environment have on their physical and mental wellness and their ability to function. The approach is used in a broad range of helping professions in health and social care setting as well as by medical and social science. People may not be fully aware of the relationship between their mental and emotional well-being and the environment. It was first commonly used by psychologists Erik Erikson in his description of the stages of psychosocial development.

Mary Richmond, pioneer of American social work regarded there to be a linear relationship between cause and effect in a diagnostic process. In 1917 concept of "Social diagnoses as psychosocial study" psychosocial study was further developed by Hollis in 1964 with emphasis in treatment model. It is contrasted with diverse social psychology, which attempts to explain social functioning can be referred to as "psychosocial dysfunction" or "psychosocial morbidity." this refers to the lack of development or diverse atrophy of the psychosocial self, often occurring alongside other dysfunctions that may be physical, emotional, or cognitive in nature.

Adolph Meyer in the late 1800s stated "we cannot understand the individual presentation of mental illness, [and perpetuating factors] without knowing how that person functions in the environment," psychosocial assessment stems from this idea.

Psychologists explore how one's personality affects the ability to perform. Personality and smart go farther than good looks. And now even psychologists are on her side. For year's psychologists turned to cognitive ability of performance: Smarter people were considered more likely to succeed. But intelligence alone is only part of the story. Creativity, leadership, integrity, attendance and cooperation also play major roles in a person's job suitability and productivity. Personality, rather than intelligence, predicts these qualities (Bandura, 1986). Armed with this belief, psychologists are trying to tease out

personality's impact on overall performance. Although they haven't unravelled the details, most agree that personality is as important as intelligence, and maybe more so, for some aspects of performance.

A strong sense of efficacy enhances human accomplishment and personal well-being in many ways. People with high assurance in their capabilities approach difficult task as challenges to be mastered rather than as threats to be avoided. Such an efficacious outlook fosters intrinsic interest and deep engrossment in activities. They set themselves challenging goals and maintain strong commitment to them. They heighten and sustain their efforts in the face of failure. They quickly recover their sense of efficacy after failures or setbacks.

Normally, if we would consider that selflessly helping others, as a form of personal growth motivation, would be found as part of self-actualization, or perhaps even 'transcendence'. (If these needs are not met, the person feels inferior, weak, helpless and worthless... Maslow describes self-actualization as 'self-actualizing' individuals. It is also explained that people who seek the frontier of creativity and strive to reach higher levels of consciousness and wisdom.

Today, women's role in the society has been a controversial issue of debate over the decades; some arguing that rapid population growth appeared to be the major obstacles for the advancement of women, while other critics blame the low status to their roles in the labor force participation. Some version of the argument noted that the home-life terribly suffers when women work, for women are faced with double burden of office or factory work followed by domestic chores and child care but in economic term, the costing of these contributions are neglected. The status of women had always been lower than men, but the extent of the gap between the sexes varies across cultures and time. As such, gender is as a social construct specifying the socially and culturally prescribed roles that men and women are to follow or biological distinction between males and females. Hence, the extent to which the society views women's roles or women are engaged in domestic activities as against gainful employment outside of the home has inverse relation to their status. There are of course numerous indicators, such as, the level of education, marital status, mortality and fertility levels, rural and urban residence, etc. that are plausibly responsible for the differential roles that men and women play, which seem to have adverse effect on women's status. However, the objective of this chapter is to examine labor force participation rates of men and women; looking at the differences and the changes during the decades, the interrelations of industry, occupation and employment status, and the differentials in household headships.

GAD Is an approach which emphasis on gender equity; honestly, it has a great effect on the system of administration we are working on. Thus, this requires the transformation of self. Not all female managers or heads have pride to face the challenges of holding the highest position in the office. For instance, it exists in an academe community. You are the only female manager. Even though how intelligent, hardworking, and resilient administrator, who assumes a great deal of responsibility quickly. But still your colleagues are doubt in your capability and credibility. There are lot of questions that will be asked. Even your decisions appeared to be strong and firm. The frustrations...you will still be regarded as no-nonsense type of manager. There is asocial issue on the matter. The stigma attached is that women had always been lower than man.

Gender and Development (GAD) refers to the development perspective and process that is participatory and empowering, equitable, sustainable, free from violence, respectful of human rights, supportive of self-determination and actualization of human potentials. It seeks to achieve gender equality as a fundamental value that should be reflected in development choices and contends that women are active agents of development, not just passive recipients of development; Also the principles asserting the equality of women and men and their right to enjoy equal conditions realizing their full human potentials to contribute to and benefit from the results of development, and with the State recognizing that all human beings are free and equal in dignity and rights; the strategy for making women's as well as men's concerns and experiences an integral dimension of the design, implementation, monitoring, and evaluation of policies, programs and projects in all social, political, civil, and economic spheres so that women and men benefit equally. It is the process of assessing the implications for women and men of any planned action, including legislation, policies or programs in all areas and at all levels; It is a goal of and an essential process for women's advancement and the process and condition by which women mobilize to understand, identify and overcome gender discrimination so as to achieve equality in welfare and equal access to resources. In this context, women become agents of development and not just beneficiaries enabling them to make decisions based on their own views and perspectives.

Agencies shall develop GAD capacity development programs that support continuing gender education, updating and enhancing skills customized according to the functions of the GFPS, to be integrated in the regular agency Human Resource Development Plan. These capacity development programs may include gender sensitivity, gender analysis, gender-responsive planning and budgeting and gender audit, among others;

The concept of school engagement has attracted increasing attention as representing a possible antidote to declining academic motivation and achievement. Engagement is presumed to be malleable, responsive to contextual features, and cognitive to contextual features, and amenable to environmental change.

The School as an Agency for Cultivating Cognitive Self-Efficacy is the crucial formative period of children's lives, the school functions as the primary setting for the cultivation and social validation of cognitive competencies. School is the place where children develop the cognitive competencies and acquire the knowledge and problem-solving skills essential for participating effectively in the larger society. Here their knowledge and thinking skills are continually tested, evaluated, and socially compared. As children master cognitive skills, they develop growing sense of their intellectual efficacy. Many social factors, apart from the formal instruction, such as peer modelling of cognitive skills and social comparison related with the performance of other students. Motivational enhancement through goals and positive incentives, and teachers' interpretations of children's successes and failures in ways that reflect favorably or unfavorably on their ability also affect children's judgments of their intellectual efficacy.

The task of creating learning environments conducive to development of cognitive skills rests heavily on the talents and self-efficacy about their teaching capabilities can motivate their students and enhance their cognitive development. Teachers who have a low sense of instructional efficacy favor a custodial orientation that relies heavily on negative sanctions to get students to study.

Teachers operate collectively within an interactive social system rather than as isolates. The belief that systems of staffs create school cultures that can have vitalizing or demoralizing effects on how well school functions as a social system. Schools in which the staffs collectively judge themselves as powerless to get students to achieve academic success are a worrisome issue.

To inspire and impel to higher endeavor, the management provides favorable communication and participation. Allen (1975) assert that people should have an opportunity to do and hear on matters that affect them, and that they should participate in the preliminary discussion and analysis of discussion that directly involve them.

Therefore, the above mentioned claims needs to be confirmed nor denied based on empirical data that can be sourced from college/university instructors. This study will endeavor to gather ascertain the perceived school-level psychosocial environment and self-efficacy of teachers at higher institutions in Sulu.

Statement of the problem

This study determined and assessed the extent of teachers' perceived school-level psychosocial environment and self-efficacy at higher education institutions in Sulu during school year 2018-2019.

Hypotheses

The following are the hypotheses that answered this study:

1. There is no significant relationship between teachers' perceived school-level psychosocial environment and self-efficacy at higher education institutions in Sulu?
2. There is no significant difference in teachers' perceived self-efficacy at higher education Institutions in Sulu when data are grouped according to: Age; Gender; Length of service; Academic rank; Educational Qualification; Employment status; and Type of HEI.
3. There is no significant difference in teachers' perceived school-level psychosocial environment at higher education Institutions in Sulu when data are grouped according to: Age; Gender; Length of service; Academic rank; Educational Qualification; Employment status; and Type of HEI.

Objectives of the Study

This study determined the significant relationship between teacher's perceived school-level psychosocial environment and self-efficacy at higher education institutions in Sulu when the respondents are classified according to age, gender, length of service, academic rank, educational qualification, employment status, and, type of HEI. Moreover, it determined if there is a significant relationship between identified determinants and the teacher's perceived school-level psychosocial environment and self-efficacy at higher education institutions in Sulu.

The general objective of this study will determine teacher's perceived school-level psychosocial environment at higher education Institutions in Sulu. Specifically, this will aim at ascertaining:

1. The demographic profile of the college faculty at higher education institutions in Sulu in terms of Age; Gender; Length of service; Academic rank; Educational Qualification; Employment status; and Type of HEI;
2. The extent of teachers' perceived school-level psychosocial environment at higher education institutions in Sulu in terms of relationship dimension, personal development dimension; and system maintenance and system change dimension;
3. The extent of teacher's perceived self-efficacy at higher education institutions in Sulu in terms of student engagement, instructional strategies; and personal teaching efficacy;
4. The degree of correlation between teachers' perceived school-level psychosocial environment and self-efficacy at higher educational institutions in Sulu;
5. The significant difference in teacher's perceived self-efficacy at higher education institutions in Sulu when data are grouped according to socio-demographic profiles; and
6. The significant difference in teacher's perceived school-level psychosocial environment at higher education institutions in Sulu when data are grouped according to socio-demographic profiles.

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on the Bandura's (1989) Efficacy Theory.

Albert Bandura (1989) stressed that perceived self-efficacy or memory functioning is an important facet of meta memory. Self-beliefs or efficacy can enhance or impair performance through their effects on cognitive, effective, or motivational intervening.

Considering how much time most children spend at school, psychosocial dimensions of Schools have parked the interest of growing number of researchers concerned with school effectiveness and emotional well-being of young people. The psychosocial learning environment covers psychological and social factors that have consequences for satisfaction, health and ability to perform at learning places. The term psychosocial aspects of our experiences (e.g. our thoughts, emotions and behaviors) and our wider social experience (e.g. our relationships, tradition and culture). Learners and teachers are psychologically affected by the surrounding social conditions that may disrupt or enhance the quality and effectiveness of learning. The question is how to endure every learner an environment that is physically safe, emotionally secure and psychologically enabling. A focus on well- being of the learner, including attention to different groups, physical ability and socio economic status, will help address disparities that steam from home and community background, creating a more level playing field.

Conceptual Framework

Based on the aforementioned theories, in this study the teachers' perceived school-level psychosocial environment of college teachers in Sulu such as a) Relationship dimension; b) Personal development dimension; and c) System maintenance and system change dimension are treated as independent variable. Meanwhile, the teachers' self-efficacy which includes a) Student engagement, b) Instructional strategies; and c) Personal teaching efficacy are treated as dependent variable. Finally, the respondents' profile is treated as the moderating variable of this study. The interplay of these variables is shown in Figure 1 below:

Figure 1. The Conceptual Model of the Study

Significance of the Study

This study will benefit the educational institutions and will permit the administrators to reflect upon their practices and make improvements, as may be needed. Result of this study shall help the administrators adjust their existing practices with the perception of knowing the teacher’s school-level psychosocial environment and self- efficacy. This will improve interactions and relations thereby promoting environment friendly and conducive for learning and work relations.

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

This study determined the significant relationship between teacher’s perceived school-level psychosocial environment and self-efficacy at higher education institutions in Sulu when the respondents are classified according to age, gender, length of service, academic rank, educational qualification, employment status, and, type of HEI. Moreover, it will determine if there is a significant relationship between identified determinants and the teacher’s perceived school-level psychosocial environment and self-efficacy at higher education institutions in Sulu.

The study is delimited to the teachers hired both in private and public Colleges and Universities in Sulu. This study dealt on the teacher’s perceived school-level psychosocial environment and self- efficacy in the higher education institutions in Sulu. Further, this study tried to determine the teachers school-level psychosocial environment and self-efficacy.

The socio-demographic profile of the respondents as herein enumerated below; 1. Age; 2. Gender; 3. Length of service; 4. Academic rank; 5. Educational Qualification; 6. Employment status; and 7. Type of HEI.

Likewise, this study is confined to the extent of teacher’s perceived school-level of psychosocial environment at higher education institutions in Sulu in each of the following categories: 1. Relationship dimension, 2. Personal development dimension; and 3. System maintenance and system change dimension and significant relationship between teacher’s school-level psychosocial environment and self-efficacy at higher education institutions in Sulu.

Six (6) schools both public and private Colleges and Universities served as the setting of the study. Two hundred (200) respondents that includes teachers at Sulu State College, Notre Dame Jolo College, Mindanao State University, Sulu College of Technology, Southwestern Muslim Islamic Institute and Hadji Butu School of Arts and Trade.

Operational Definition of Terms

Age – refers to the chronological age of the respondents. In this study, the age of the respondents will be categorized into four brackets such as: 30 years old and below; 31 to 35 years old; 36 to 40 years old; and 41 years old and above.

Gender – refers to the biological traits of the respondents. In this study, the gender of respondents will be categorized as male and female.

Educational Qualification – refers to highest level of school that the respondents have attained. In this study, it is classified into five brackets: a) plain baccalaureate degree which is either Bachelor of Arts (BS) or Bachelor of Science (BS); b) AB/BS plus some units in master's program; c) Full-fledged Master of Arts or Master of Science (MA/MS); d) MA/MS plus some units in doctoral program; and e) Full-fledged Doctor of Education (Ed.D.) or Doctor of Philosophy (Ph.D.)

Length of Service - refers to the number of years of experience in teaching. In this study, the length of service will be categorized into four groups such as: 10 years and below; 11 - 20 years; and 21 years and above.

Employment Status – refers to the nature of employment of teachers. In this study, teachers' employment status will be classified as contractual, temporary and permanent.

Teaching Efficacy – refers to the overall ability of the teacher to undergo effective facilitation of the lesson in the classroom. In this study, it involves the ways junior and senior high school teachers in Sulu facilitate classroom teaching activities.

Efficacy for student engagement – refers to the ability of the teacher on how to get learners involve in the classroom activities. In this study, it involves how junior and senior high school teachers engage students to participate actively in classroom teaching activities.

Efficacy for classroom management – refers to the ability of the teacher to manage learners in order to follow rules and regulations. In this study, it involves how junior and senior high school teachers in Sulu manage the disrupting behavior of the students.

Personal Efficacy – refers to the ability of the teacher to adopt alternative strategies to make classroom instructive more effective. In this study, generally, it involves how college teachers in Sulu facilitate varied instructional techniques so as to arrive at more effective classroom dynamics.

II. REVIEW OF RELATED STUDIES

This study deals with the related literature and studies on determinants of teachers' perceived school-level psychosocial environment and self-efficacy in higher education institutions in Sulu.

In the last two decades, the proportion of the work force that is female has been increasingly at a rapid pace. In 1990, approximately 33 percentage of the labor force was female; currently, the percentage is somewhat in excess of 40 percentages and still growing. Some of this increase can be attributed to changes in cultural beliefs and norms; yet the assurance of greater opportunities through the civil rights legislation has also contributed to these increased numbers. Since 1964 there have been numerous major Federal Court decisions issued regarding the employment of females. Among the legalities discovered are: (1) refusal to hire woman, but not men, with young children; (2) refusal to hire married woman; (3) refusal to hire a female because she might become pregnant; (4) discharging an unmarried pregnant female; (5) requiring pregnant employees to take leave without regard to ability to perform the job; (6) refusal to hire females because heavy weight must be lifted; and, (7) taking away seniority rights after pregnancy leave (Flippo, 1984).

The Civil Rights Act specially provides for the possibility of a bona fide occupational qualification (BFOQ) in regards to gender. One may specify hiring a male or female for the job of actor or actress. In the case of *Dothard V. Rawlinson*, a female applicant for a job of correctional counsellor in an Alabama State prison was turned down because she could not meet the state 5'2", 120-pounds minimum requirement. It was shown that these minimum excluded 41 percentage of the female population of the United States while excluding less than 1 percentage of the males. The court went on to specify that gender, rather than height and weight was a BFOQ because of the jungle nature of state prison. It was determined that female's ability to maintain order in a male, maximum- security penitentiary would be directly reduced by her woman blood. Despite the law and many specific legal decisions, it is true that equal opportunity is denied to female employees in many subtle ways on a daily basis (Rosen and Jerdee, 1974).

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III. METHOD: RESEARCH BLUEPRINT

This chapter presents the research design, respondents, research instrument, data gathering procedure, sampling procedure, and statistical treatment of data used in this study.

Research Design

The descriptive method of research, employing the questionnaire checklist, which is patterned from previous studies with some modifications to suit the present study, was used.

Research Locale

This study was conducted in Sulu by utilizing the college teachers during the school year 2018-2019 as the target respondents. These higher educational institutions are located in the Province of Sulu.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents of this study were taken from Teachers of higher education institutions both private and public colleges and universities, such as Notre Dame Jolo College, Sulu State College, Mindanao State Universities, Hadji Butu School of Arts and Trade, Sulu College of Technology, and Southern Mindanao Islamic Institute. It used purposive and simple random sampling technique from the total population of the selected higher educational institutions in Sulu. Thirty three (33) respondents were targeted for every institution.

Distribution of samples according to types of respondents is shown below

HEIs	Gender		Total
	Male	Female	
Private	63		63
Notre Dame Jolo College	15	17	
Sulu College of Technology	17	19	
SMII	12	15	
Public	137		137
Sulu State College	18	21	
Mindanao State Universities	15	23	
HBSAT	13	18	
Total	90	110	200

Sampling Design

Purposive and simple random sampling procedures were adopted in this study. That is, due to access, availability and time constrains, representative samples from private and public higher education institutions in Sulu were chosen purposively as samples of this study. The use of purposive sampling procedure was employed to ensure the collection of desired quality and quantity of data that were used in this study.

Data Gathering Procedure

In the collection of data, the following steps were applied in this study:

1. A permit to administer the questionnaire was secured from the Dean of the School of Graduate Studies of the Sulu State College and then from the presidents, chancellors and head colleges and universities in Sulu; and
2. The launching and administering as well as the retrieval of the questionnaire were done personally by the researcher.

Research Instrument

A self-report questionnaire was the main instrument used to gather data on teachers' demographic profiles, teachers' perceived school-level psychosocial environment and self-efficacy. The Teacher Self-Efficacy (Tschannen- Moran & Woolfolk Hoy, 2001) Adapted version of the self-reported strategy scale (Moe et al., 2001) was the main research instrument adopted in collecting data from the respondents of this study.

There are three parts of the research instrument used in this study. First part of the questionnaire focused on collection of data on the socio-demographic profiles of teacher-respondents which includes age, gender; educational attainment, length of service, employment status, position and types of HEI. The second part dealt with the collection of data on teachers' teaching efficacy which includes a) Efficacy for student engagement, b) Efficacy for classroom management, and c) Personal Efficacy. The third part of the questionnaire used to gather data on teachers' perceived school-level psychosocial environment to include a) Relationship dimension; b) Personal development dimension; and c) System maintenance and system change dimension.

Validity and Reliability

The research instrument used in this study was patterned and adapted from the short version of the Teacher Self-Efficacy (Tschannen-Moran & Woolfolk Hoy, 2001) an adapted version of the self-reported strategy scale (Moe et al., 2001). This was the main research instrument used in collecting data from the target respondents. These Questionnaires were already adopted in both foreign and local studies, thus their validity and reliability are already established. However, to suit its applicability with the setting of the present study, this research instrument was subjected for perusal of at least two experts from among the faculty members of the School of Graduate Studies of the Sulu State College.

Statistical Treatment

Both descriptive and inferential statistical tools were employed in the treatments of data to be gathered for this study, namely:

- 1) Mean, percentages and standard deviation were employed to determine the following: the socio-demographic profiles of both junior and senior high school teachers in terms of age, gender, length of service, position, educational attainment, employment status and types of HEI.
- 2) *t*-test for independent samples was employed to determine the significant difference in both HEI teachers' perceived school-level psychosocial environment and self-efficacy and when data are grouped according to gender and types of HEI;
- 3) One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was employed to determine the significant differences in teachers' perceived school-level psychosocial environment and self-efficacy when data are grouped according to age, length of service, position, educational attainment, and employment status.
- 4) Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (Pearson *r*) test was employed to determine the significant correlation among the sub-categories subsumed under teachers' perceived school-level psychosocial environment and self-efficacy.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This chapter deals with the presentation, analyses and interpretation of results based on the data obtained for this study. It also tackles the extent, relationship and differences of teachers' perceived school-level psychosocial environment and self-efficacy at higher education institutions in Sulu during school year 2018-2019 when data are grouped according to sex, age, length of service, position, highest educational qualification, status of appointment and type of higher educational institution.

V. SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter tackles with the summary, findings, conclusions and recommendations based on proper computation and thorough analyses of data gathered for this study.

Summary

This study determined the extent of perceived self-efficacy and school-level psychosocial environment among college instructors at higher education institutions in Sulu during school year 2018-2019 and the significant relationship and differences in categories subsumed under these components when data are grouped according to age, gender, civil status, length of service, academic rank, highest educational qualification and type of higher education institution.

This study answered the research questions based on the following hypotheses: (1) There is no significant relationship between teacher's perceived school-level psychosocial environment and self-efficacy at higher education institutions in

Sulu; (2) There is no significant difference in teacher's perceived self-efficacy at higher education Institutions in Sulu when data are grouped according to: Age; Gender; Length of service; Academic rank; Educational Qualification; Employment status; and Type of HEI. (3) There is no significant difference in teacher's perceived school-level psychosocial environment at higher education Institutions in Sulu when data are grouped according to: Age; Gender; Length of service; Academic rank; Educational Qualification; Employment status; and Type of HEI.

This study employed the descriptive-quantitative research design with 200 college instructors at higher education institutions in Sulu during the school year 2018-2019. The frequency counts and percentage score were used to determine the socio-demographic profiles; mean and standard deviation were used to determine the extent of teaching efficacy and school-level psychosocial environment. The *t*-Test for independent samples, One-Way ANOVA and Pearson Correlation Coefficient were used to determine the significant differences and degree of correlation of these variables.

Findings

The following are findings of the study:

1. On students' demographic profile

- 1.1. In terms of age, 40.5% of the instructors belong to age range of 31-40 years old;
- 1.2. In terms of gender, female college instructors constitute 55.0% while their male counterparts constitute 45.0% of the total 200 samples;
- 1.3. In terms of length of service, 47.0% have 10 years & below years of experience;
- 1.4. In terms of academic rank, 45.5% are Instructor (I, II, and III);
- 1.5. In terms of highest educational attainment, 30.0% are having AB/BS + MA/MS Units;
- 1.6. In terms of employment status, 29.5% are contractual/job order and 44.0% with permanent status; and
- 1.7. In terms of type of HEI, 68.5% are public higher education institutions.

2. On extent of Teachers' self-efficacy

- 2.1 On Efficacy for Student Engagement – instructors rated this category as Moderate Extent.
- 2.2 On Instructional Strategies - instructors rated this category as Moderate Extent.
- 2.3 On Personal Teaching Efficacy - instructors rated this category as Moderate Extent.

3. On Extent of School-level Psychosocial environment:

- 3.1 On Relationship Dimension - instructors rated this category as High Extent.
- 3.2 On Personal Development Dimension – instructors rated this category as High Extent.
- 3.3 On System Maintenance/System Change Dimension - instructors rated this category as High Extent.

4. On Correlation between Teachers' Self-Efficacy and School-Level Psychosocial environment:

- 4.1 There is "Near Zero Correlation" between teachers' self-efficacy and school-level psychosocial environment.

5. On differences in Teachers' Self-Efficacy

5.1 By Age, There is significant difference in teacher's perceived self-efficacy at higher education institutions in Sulu when data are grouped according to Age; Age 30 years & below are better perceivers of the extent of teaching efficacy in terms of student engagement; but age 21 years & above are better perceivers extent of teaching efficacy in terms of personal teaching efficacy.

5.2 By Gender, No significant difference in teacher's perceived self-efficacy at higher education institutions in Sulu when data are grouped according to gender.

5.3 By Length of Service, There is significant difference in teacher's perceived self-efficacy at higher education institutions in Sulu when data are grouped according to length of service. Instructors with 21 years & above of teaching experience are better perceivers the extent of teaching efficacy in terms of student engagement.

5.4 By Academic Rank, There is significant difference in teacher's perceived self-efficacy at higher education institutions in Sulu when data are grouped according to academic rank. Instructors with academic rank of a Prof. (I, II, III, IV, V, and VI) are better perceivers of the extent of teaching efficacy in terms of student engagement.

5.5 By Educational Attainment, No significant difference in teacher's perceived self-efficacy at higher education institutions in Sulu when data are grouped according to educational attainment.

5.6 By Employment Status, There is significant difference in teacher's perceived self-efficacy at higher education institutions in Sulu when data are grouped according to employment status. Instructors with permanent status of appointment are better perceivers of extent of teaching efficacy in terms of student engagement; instructional strategies and personal teaching efficacy.

5.7 By Type of HEI, There is significant difference in teacher's perceived self-efficacy at higher education institutions in Sulu when data are grouped according to type of higher educational institution.

6. Difference in School-level Psychosocial Environment

6.1 By Age, There is significant difference in school-level psychosocial environment at higher education institutions in Sulu when data are grouped according to Age. With 30 years and below of age are better perceivers of the extent of school-level psychosocial environment in terms of relationship dimension, personal development dimension and System Maintenance.

6.2 By Gender, There is significant difference in teacher's perceived school-level psychosocial environment at higher education institutions in Sulu when data are grouped according to gender.

6.3 By Length of service, there is significant difference in teacher's perceived school-level psychosocial environment at higher education institutions in Sulu when data are grouped according to length of service. With 10 years & below of length are better perceivers of the extent of school-level psychosocial environment in terms of relationship dimension, personal development dimension and System Maintenance.

6.4 By Academic Rank, No significant difference in teacher's perceived school-level psychosocial environment at higher education institutions in Sulu when data are grouped according to academic rank'

6.5 By Educational Qualification, No significant difference in teacher's perceived school-level psychosocial environment at higher education institutions in Sulu when data are grouped according to educational attainment

6.6 By Employment Status, There is significant difference in teacher's perceived school-level psychosocial environment at higher education institutions in Sulu when data are grouped according to employment status. Contractual/Job Order status of appointment are better perceivers of the extent of school-level psychosocial environment in terms of relationship dimension and System Maintenance.

6.7 By Type of HEI, There is significant difference in teacher's perceived school-level psychosocial environment at higher education institutions in Sulu when data are grouped according to type of higher educational institution.

Conclusions

Respondents of this study are at age range of 31-40 years old; majority are female, have 10 years & below years of experience; Instructor (I, II, and III); having AB/BS + MA/MS Units; permanent status; and at public higher education institutions.

Teachers' self-efficacy is moderately rated, while school-level psychosocial environment rated as high extent with Near Zero Correlation between them. Yet, educational attainment, academic rank and gender have no influence on respondent's perceptions towards teachers' self-efficacy and school-level psychosocial environment.

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This particular study seems to support Bandura's (1989) Efficacy Theory when he stressed that the perceived self-efficacy or memory functioning is an important facet of meta-memory. Self-beliefs or efficacy can enhance or impair performance through their effects on cognitive, effective, or motivational intervening.

Moreover, Bandura (1989) said that the psychosocial learning environment covers psychological and social factors that have consequences for satisfaction, health and ability to perform at learning places. The term psychosocial aspects of our experiences (e.g. our thoughts, emotions and behaviors) and our wider social experience (e.g. our relationships, tradition and culture). Learners and teachers are psychologically affected by the surrounding social conditions that may disrupt or enhance the quality and effectiveness of learning. The question is how to endure every learner an environment that is physically safe, emotionally secure and psychologically enabling.

Recommendations

Higher education institutions in the province Sulu may venture into reviewing the programs and activities to include those that cater to the improvement of social learning environment of college students; prompt and adequacy of overload pay; Processes and programs to reduce job insecurity. The educational attainment and academic rank showed significant effect to school-level psychosocial environment, thus it is mostly recommended that the faculty should pursue advance education in their field of specialization.

Issues and concerns relating to provision of conducive social learning should be given a serious attention. That is, public higher education institutions should devise programs and strategies that shall promote better learning conditions via individual and work interventions.

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